

Determination of Rare Earth Elements in Geological Samples by Inductively Coupled Plasma—Mass Spectrometry

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Rare earth element (REE) concentrations of international reference silicate standards have been determined by inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS). The high sensitivity of the ICP-MS and small number of interferences which are predictable, allow the estimation of these elements directly in 0.1% rock solutions without ion exchange separation or pre-concentration. Precisions of 1–7% relative standard deviation (RSD) and comparable accuracy are obtained. Comparison of the results with the recommended values demonstrates the suitability of this method for precise REE analysis of geological materials for geochemical applications

RARE earth element (REE) abundances in geological materials have assumed considerable importance in geochemical research¹. Recent developments in petrogenetic modelling call for a precise and rapid method of determination of REE in a variety of geological materials. However, quantitative determination of REE in these materials is rendered difficult by their typically low abundance levels (generally 0.1–10 $\mu\text{g/g}$). Methods such as atomic absorption spectrometry (AAS) and X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy (XRF) have not proved successful in the analysis of REE in silicate rocks because of several reasons¹. Other techniques like thermal ionisation isotope dilution mass spectrometry (IDMS)², spark source mass spectrometry (SSMS)³ and neutron activation analysis (NAA)⁴ have been used successfully for the REE analysis in geological samples. In recent years, inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectroscopy (ICP-AES) has emerged as a viable alternative analytical method for REE analysis in geological materials^{5,6}. However, this technique generally requires prior separation and pre-concentration of REE. These limitations have been overcome in the inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) which has gained considerable application due to the high sensitivity and limited interferences⁷.

Previous work on the estimation of REE in geological samples^{8,9} demonstrated the potential of ICP-MS for the determination of REE in solutions of acid digested geological samples without prior separation and pre-concentration of these elements from the silicate matrix and by using only simple aqueous reference standard solutions⁷. However, there is a need for more work in this direction as the technique is relatively new. This paper deals with the details of analytical procedures and the results of REE estimations in some international rock

standards by ICP-MS using samples prepared by acid decomposition and fusion methods. The problems associated with the stability of the signal and possible methods to overcome such problems are also presented.

Experimental

The ICP-MS used in this study is a VG Plasma-Quad (VG Elemental Ltd., U.K.). The ion detection system and the data acquisition system consist of a Channeltron Electron Multiplier (CEM) and a multi-channel analyser (Tracor Northern). An on-line IBM PC/XT microcomputer facilitates data acquisition, processing and storage. The details of operation parameters of the instrument are summarised elsewhere¹⁰.

Standards and samples : The standard reference materials (SRM) analysed in this work include : syenite SY-2 and gabbro MRG-1 from Canadian Certified Reference Materials Project (CCRMP) ; basalt BCR-1 from United States Geological Survey (USGS). High purity single element spectroscopic solutions of La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm, Eu, Gd, Tb, Dy, Ho, Er, Tm, Yb, Lu, Mg, Co, Pb, Ba and In at concentrations of 1000 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ (Alfa) were used. The calibration standard multi-element solutions were prepared in 5% (v/v) HNO_3 from these solutions.

Sample preparation and internal standardisation : Dissolution of sample was accomplished by the following methods. (i) *Acid decomposition method* : Rock sample solutions (0.1%) were prepared using $\text{HF}-\text{HClO}_4-\text{HNO}_3$ decomposition procedure in teflon beakers. An acid concentration of 5% (v/v) was maintained with respect to HNO_3 with an overall concentration of 0.1 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ indium to serve as internal standard. (ii) *Fusion method* : A sample

of rock powder (0.1 g) and lithium tetraborate (0.5 g) were fused in a platinum crucible (5% gold) in a muffle furnace at 1000° for 30 min. The contents were dissolved using minimum amount of nitric acid and diluted to 500 ml, keeping the acid concentration at 5% (v/v) and the concentration of internal standard at 0.1 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. Clear solutions were obtained in all cases. Double-distilled water and acids (AnalaR/electronic grade) were used in preparation of the standards, samples and blanks.

To compensate for any variations in instrument sensitivity, electronic drift, nebuliser efficiency, total salt content and other matrix effects, the technique of internal standardisation is extensively used in ICP-AES¹¹. This method has been observed to be useful in ICP-MS analysis also¹². Indium (¹¹⁵In) is particularly suited for this purpose in geochemical samples mainly because of its very low abundance levels (about 60 ng g^{-1}) and also because of its low first ionisation potential (5.79 eV) and a high second ionisation potential (18.86 eV) which is much higher than the first ionisation potential of the plasma gas, namely, argon (15.76 eV). Indium forms mainly singly-charged species under plasma conditions and the concentration of doubly-charged species are generally insignificant. Accordingly all solutions in this study contained identical (100 ng ml^{-1}) concentrations of indium to serve as internal standard.

Data acquisition: Sample solutions were introduced into the instrument by conventional pneumatic nebulisation. A multi-element solution containing 100 ng ml^{-1} each of magnesium, cobalt, indium, lanthanum, and lead was used to obtain a uniform response across the mass range by optimising the signals at the masses ²⁴Mg, ⁵⁹Co, ¹¹⁵In, ¹³⁹La and ²⁰⁸Pb. Under these conditions the instrument response for most elements was typically 1.65×10^5 counts/s. Solutions were introduced via an eight-roller peristaltic pump at a rate of 1.0 ml min^{-1} and the system was operated in the mass scanning mode in the mass range m/z 113–179 covering all the fourteen rare earth elements and the internal standard. Under these conditions a complete spectrum gets accumulated in just over 2 min. Each standard or sample solution or blank was aspirated for about 2 min for the system equilibration and to avoid any possible memory effects before data acquisition. Calibration curves obtained by counting on 10, 50 and 100 ng ml^{-1} solutions of REE with internal standard were used in estimations of REE in unknown solutions.

Results and Discussion

Interference effects: The operating conditions chosen in this work offered minimal interference effects from both oxides and doubly-charged ionic species. The oxide formation levels of barium and other interfering REE were found to be varying from 0.2% (BaO^+/Ba^+) to 0.08% (TbO^+/Tb^+) and the degree of doubly-charged ion formation was found to be

<2% for all REE. These levels are considered to have minimal interference effect on the REE estimations.

Sensitivity and detection limits: Table 1 gives the detection limits (3σ standard deviation of the background) on the indicated REE peaks calculated from the signals obtained on 100 ng ml^{-1} multi-element synthetic standard solution and a 0.1% solution of BCR-1, together with the REE abundances in chondrite meteorites. The detection limits found in this study were consistent with the published values. Obviously the detection limits are affected by a factor of two in the rock matrix. In general for successful determination, the analytes should have background concentrations at least ten times their detection limit. Since the detection limits in the rock solutions are significantly lower than the REE abundances in the chondrites, the method is suitable for REE estimations even in samples with very low REE abundances.

TABLE 1—REE DETECTION LIMITS BY ICP-MS TECHNIQUE WITH CHONDRITE VALUES

Element	Mass	ICP-MS detection limit values (ng/g)		Chondrite value in $\mu\text{g/g}^c$
		In synthetic multi-element solution ^a	In rock matrix ^b	
La	139	0.100	0.183	0.315
Ce	140	0.015	0.033	0.813
Pr	141	0.010	0.027	0.110
Nd	146	0.050	0.070	0.597
Sm	147	0.036	0.042	0.192
Eu	151	0.017	0.032	0.0722
Gd	157	0.012	0.064	0.259
Tb	159	0.009	0.017	0.047
Dy ³	163	0.024	0.047	0.325
Ho	165	0.010	0.016	0.070
Er	167	0.028	0.056	0.213
Tm	169	0.009	0.019	0.030
Yb	173	0.025	0.040	0.208
Lu	175	0.008	0.016	0.0323

^aUsing 100 ng/ml multi-element solution of all the fourteen elements. ^bUsing 0.1% solution of BCR-1. ^cRef. 22.

Calibration, precision and accuracy: The calibration curves are found to be linear in the working range of this study. The proposed acid decomposition method worked well for the REE analysis for different types of rock samples considered in this work. The fusion method described here also yielded comparable results to that of acid decomposition procedure. For instance, Table 2 provides comparative REE data for these two sample dissolution methods on SY-2 together with the reported data. The data is reasonably consistent with the reported values in the case of both methods. This agreement between acid digestion and lithium tetraborate fusion sample preparation methods shows that both the methods are useful for REE analysis by ICP-MS. However, the magnitude of drift (sometimes upto more than 50%) on the analytical signal observed is more in the case of the sample prepared

by fusion method. Only signal suppression was observed in the case of samples prepared by fusion method whereas both signal suppression and enhancement effects were observed in the case of samples by acid dissolution methods with suppression being more frequent which is believed to be due to sample deposition at the sample orifice¹³. There have been some conflicting reports in the literature on these effects¹⁴. The processes governing these effects are currently under investigation¹⁵. Because of the lower blanks and low total dissolved salts, the acid digestion procedure is usually preferred wherever possible. Acid dissolution procedure is more convenient and rapid particularly when large number of samples are being prepared. But, it is suggested to have a check by the fusion method especially when resistant minerals such as zircon, monazite, zirconium, rutile, chromite etc. which contain large concentrations of REEs are suspected to be present in the samples.

The standard-addition method is more time-consuming compared to the three-point calibration and background correction method adopted in this

study especially when multi-element analysis is required. For each standard-addition analysis at least two spiked solutions and the sample solution together with a blank sample must be run in order to yield the concentration of only one element in an unknown sample. In this study, the procedure was adopted for measuring REE concentrations in MRG-1. Comparable results were obtained for all REE in MRG-1 (Table 2). The precision of the present work was found to be better than 5% for all the REE. The precisions obtained here are comparable with those obtained by McLaren and others for the estimation of trace metals in marine sediments by ICP-MS¹⁶.

The precisions and accuracies are demonstrated on USGS basalt standard BCR-1. The REE data obtained by analysing 0.1% solution of BCR-1 are presented in Table 3. The analytical accuracy may be assessed by the comparison of values recommended by Govindaraju¹⁷. The data obtained by ICP-MS technique are in good agreement with that obtained on the same sample by other well-established techniques for REE, like IDMS¹⁸,

TABLE 2—REE RESULTS ($\mu\text{g/g}$) OBTAINED BY ICP-MS

Element	SY-2		Reported value ¹⁷	MRG-1		Reported value ¹⁷	%RSD ^d
	Present study ^a			Present study ^b			
	(1)	(2)		Direct measurement	Standard addition		
La	72.47	73.89	75	9.63	9.50	9.8	0.69
Ce	163.5	165.32	175	26.33	26.10	26	1.13
Pr	20.06	20.35	18.8	3.82	3.90	3.4	1.55
Nd	80.56	79.77	73	18.30	18.42	19.2	0.92
Sm	16.42	16.34	16.1	4.42	4.48	4.5	2.33
Eu	2.53	2.61	2.42	1.34	1.39	1.39	2.91
Gd	17.48	16.84	17	4.35	4.29	4	2.47
Tb	3.03	2.95	2.5	0.43	0.40	0.51	4.59
Dy	20.33	20.50	18	2.54	2.50	2.9	3.34
Ho	4.55	4.60	3.8	0.46	0.51	0.49	6.84
Er	14.65	14.75	12.4	1.04	1.09	1.12	4.42
Tm	2.37	2.41	2.1	0.15	0.14	0.11	4.00
Yb	17.31	17.70	17	1.05	1.04	0.16	1.12
Lu	2.95	3.00	2.7	0.17	0.19	0.1	4.34

^a(1) Acid decomposition method, (2) fusion method; Average of three determinations.

^bAverage of six determinations. ^cRef. 17. ^dRSD=Relative standard deviation.

TABLE 3—ANALYTICAL RESULTS ($\mu\text{g/g}$) OF STANDARD ROCK BCR-1

Element	Present study ^a	ICP-AES ^b	IDMS ^c	NAA ^d	Reported value ^e
La	25.59 ± 0.18	23 ± 0.60	24.4 ± 0.20	25.2 ± 1.00	24.9
Ce	53.97 ± 0.61	52.5 ± 0.70	54.2 ± 0.40	54.2 ± 1.20	53.7
Pr	7.00 ± 0.08	6.26 ± 0.09	—	—	6.8
Nd	29.03 ± 0.26	27.5 ± 0.5	28.8 ± 0.20	30.5 ± 4.30	28.8
Sm	6.79 ± 0.16	6.04 ± 0.04	6.72 ± 0.04	7.23 ± 0.37	6.59
Eu	2.07 ± 0.06	1.96 ± 0.02	1.98 ± 0.00	1.97 ± 0.04	1.95
Gd	7.67 ± 0.19	6.23 ± 0.01	6.67 ± 0.02	8.02 ± 1.29	6.68
Tb	1.07 ± 0.05	—	—	—	1.05
Dy	6.39 ± 0.21	5.99 ± 0.04	6.36 ± 0.02	6.55 ± 1.41	6.34
Ho	1.14 ± 0.08	1.25 ± 0.01	—	—	1.28
Er	3.62 ± 0.16	3.33 ± 0.03	3.70 ± 0.02	3.51 ± 0.88	3.63
Tm	0.57 ± 0.02	—	—	—	0.56
Yb	3.39 ± 0.04	3.19 ± 0.03	3.40 ± 0.03	3.48 ± 0.12	3.38
Lu	0.48 ± 0.02	0.51 ± 0.01	0.503 ± 0.004	0.526 ± 0.15	0.51

^aAverage of six determinations. ^bRef. 20. ^cRef. 18. ^dRef. 19. ^eRef. 17.

NAA¹⁹ and ICP-AES²⁰ methods. The average precisions obtained in this study for different REE (Table 2) are also significantly better than the precisions reported recently by Jarvis²¹ using ICP-MS where the precisions obtained are better than 10% RSD. It is believed that this significant improvement in the analytical precision has been possible because of the internal standardisation procedure adopted in the present work.

Smooth chondrite-normalised²² patterns obtained using the values obtained in this study for SY-2, MRG-1 and BCR-1 further support the credibility of the ICP-MS results and suggest that the data possess the required accuracy and precision for petrogenetic studies. Smooth chondrite-normalised patterns were also obtained using the REE data obtained by this method on many other international rock reference samples and several other Indian rock types²³⁻²⁵ including Archaean greywackes from North Western part of Chitradurga schist belt, Karnataka²⁶.

Conclusions : Although ICP-MS is a reasonable choice for the REE determination in rock samples without separation from rock matrix and preconcentration, clearly it suffers from the limitation of non-tolerance to high salt contents. More than 0.4% of total dissolved solids cause clogging of the sampler and skimmer cones. For all practical purposes running of 0.1% solutions is recommended for obtaining reasonable long-term stability as it was followed in this study. The other major problem experienced is the drift in the signal with time (both suppression and enhancement) which is monitored and compensated by the use of indium as internal standard. Despite these problems, the results presented in this work clearly demonstrate the suitability of ICP-MS for the estimation of REE in rock samples with the precisions and accuracies required for most geochemical interpretations.

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